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LEXICAL UNITS OF VERBS EXPRESSING EMOTION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Abstract: This article examines the contrasting ways that emotions and feelings are expressed and valued in Uzbekistan and the United States. Grounded in distinct cultural backgrounds, Uzbeks often prioritize social harmony, restraint, and respect for others in emotional management, with a focus on community and family values. In contrast, Americans emphasize openness and individualism, where personal expression and transparency are seen as keys to healthy relationships and self-discovery. By exploring these cultural differences, the article sheds light on how diverse social norms shape emotional landscapes, providing insight into the unique ways that Uzbeks and Americans experience and navigate their feelings.

Key words: Cross-cultural emotions, Emotional expression, Uzbek culture, American culture, Emotional management, Social harmony, Individualism, Interpersonal connections, Cultural values.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston va Amerikadagi his-tuyg'ular va his-tuyg'ularni ifodalash va qadrlashning usullari ko'rib chiqiladi. Turli madaniy kelib chiqishlarga asoslangan o'zbeklar ko'pincha jamiyat va oilaviy qadriyatlarga e'tibor qaratib, hissiy boshqaruvda ijtimoiy uyg'unlik, cheklov va boshqalarga hurmat qilishni birinchi o'ringa qo'yadi. Bundan farqli o'laroq, amerikaliklar ochiqlik va individualizmni yoqlashadi, bu yerda

shaxsiy ifoda va ochiqlik sogʻlom munosabatlar va oʻz-oʻzini kashf etishning kaliti sifatida koʻriladi. Ushbu madaniy farqlarni oʻrganish orqali maqola turli xil ijtimoiy meʼyorlar hissiy tuygʻularni qanday shakllantirayotganini yoritib, oʻzbek va amerikaliklarning oʻz his-tuygʻularini boshdan kechirishlari va yoʻnaltirishlari haqida tushuncha beradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Madaniyatlararo his-tuygʻular, Hissiy ifoda, Oʻzbek madaniyati, Amerika madaniyati, Hissiyot menejmenti, Ijtimoiy uygʻunlik, Individualizm, Madaniy qadriyatlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются контрастные способы выражения и оценки эмоций и чувств в Узбекистане и США. Имея различные культурные корни, узбеки часто отдают приоритет социальной гармонии, сдержанности и уважению к другим в управлении эмоциями, уделяя особое внимание общественным и семейным ценностям. В отличие от них, американцы делают акцент на открытости и индивидуализме, где личное самовыражение и прозрачность рассматриваются как ключи к здоровым отношениям и самопознанию. Исследуя эти культурные различия, статья проливает свет на то, как различные социальные нормы формируют эмоциональные ландшафты, давая представление об уникальных способах, которыми узбеки и американцы переживают и ориентируются в своих чувствах.

Ключевые слова: Межкультурные эмоции, Эмоциональное выражение, Узбекская культура, Американская культура, Управление эмоциями, Социальная гармония, Индивидуализм, Межличностные связи, Культурные ценности.

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Emotions and feelings are central to the human experience, yet how they are expressed, managed, and valued often varies significantly across cultures. The cultural landscapes of Uzbekistan and the United States, shaped by distinct histories, values, and societal norms, offer a fascinating contrast in emotional expression. This article explores these differences, looking at how Uzbeks and Americans approach emotions, view interpersonal connections, and find meaning in life.

Uzbekistan-Uzbekistan, located at the heart of Central Asia, has a rich history influenced by Persian, Turkic, and Russian cultures. Its values are grounded in respect for tradition,

family, and community. Emotions in Uzbekistan are often managed with an emphasis on social harmony, with public displays of strong emotions generally toned down. Uzbek culture places a high value on modesty and respect for others' feelings, often fostering an environment where emotions are controlled and restrained, especially in public settings.

United States-In the United States, a culture rooted in individualism prevails, emphasizing personal expression and self-identity. Americans tend to value openness and transparency in emotional expression, seeing it as a path to self-discovery and healthy

relationships. This approach often fosters a cultural environment where expressing feelings openly—whether joy, sorrow, anger, or excitement—is seen as a sign of authenticity.

In Uzbekistan, happiness and joy are often expressed in communal settings such as family gatherings, weddings, and other significant celebrations. Shared experiences foster a sense of unity and cultural identity. However, individual expressions of success or happiness are sometimes downplayed to avoid the appearance of arrogance. Humility and respect for others are central values, influencing people to keep expressions of joy measured and inclusive.

In contrast, Americans frequently express happiness and success openly, viewing personal achievements as a reflection of individual effort. The U.S. culture values self-confidence and encourages individuals to “take pride” in their achievements, with emotional expressions in the form of celebrations, social media posts, and vocal affirmations being the norm.

Uzbek society places a high value on maintaining a peaceful and harmonious community, and this can influence the way negative emotions, such as anger or sadness, are managed. Expressing these emotions openly, especially in public, may be seen as disruptive or disrespectful. As a result, Uzbeks might prefer to manage negative feelings privately, sharing them only with close family or friends. This approach reflects a collective mentality,

where the individual considers the impact of their actions on the group.

In the United States, people are more likely to address negative emotions openly and to seek professional help when dealing with mental health issues. The American approach to negative emotions often involves seeking resolution through direct communication, therapy, or personal introspection. This openness is partly influenced by a societal focus on individual well-being and mental health awareness, which has become more mainstream over recent decades.

Expressing emotions with Gestures: People often express emotions through gestures, conveying feelings without words. A smile or open arms can show joy and warmth, while slumped shoulders or downcast eyes might signal sadness. Anger is often visible through clenched fists or pointed gestures, while surprise appears with raised eyebrows and widened eyes. Fear or anxiety might show in fidgeting or avoiding eye contact, while affection

comes through hugs, hand-holding, or gentle touches. Confident people often use open, relaxed postures and steady eye contact. These gestures reveal emotions universally, though meanings can vary across cultures.

In conclusion the directness in emotional expression seen in the U.S. contrasts sharply with the subtlety in Uzbekistan. While Americans may express feelings openly to build trust and understanding, Uzbeks may find subtlety and discretion more respectful and considerate in social and professional settings. Despite these differences, both cultures value connection and warmth—Americans express this openly, while Uzbeks express it more conservatively, especially in public. Lastly, in both cultures, emotional expression varies significantly based on the setting, with Americans being more open across contexts and Uzbeks displaying more discretion and formality, especially in public.

Some expressions to define emotions

1. Euphoria	An intense feeling of happiness or elation.
2. Jubilation	A sense of triumphant joy, often following success.
3. Contentment	A state of quiet satisfaction and ease.
4. Rapture	Ecstatic pleasure or delight, almost like being carried away by emotion.
5. Exultation	Lively or triumphant joy, typically after overcoming a challenge.
6. Serenity	A feeling of peace and calmness.
7. Bliss	Supreme happiness and inner joy.
8. Fondness	A warm affection or liking for someone or something.
9. Adoration	Deep love and respect, often expressed with admiration.
10. Amity	Warm friendliness or peaceful harmony, often in relationships.
11. Enchantment	Captivated or charmed, often by someone or something inspiring awe.
12. Despondency	A state of low spirits caused by loss of hope.
13. Melancholy	A deep, reflective sadness, often with a poetic or nostalgic tone.
14. Sorrow	Profound distress caused by loss or regret.

15. Languor	A pleasant melancholic mood, often associated with weariness.
16. Bereavement	The state of grief after losing someone close.
17. Pensive	Thoughtful and reflective, often tinged with sadness
18. Yearning	A deep longing, often for something unattainable.

19. Wrath	Intense anger, often with a sense of retribution.
20. Ire	Great anger or rage.

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